

Erroneous (overestimated by at least a factor of 2) charge carrier mobility of a perovskite transistor and several other false statements in Liu, A., Zhu, H. & Noh, YY. Reply to: Safe practices for mobility evaluation in field-effect transistors and Hall effect measurements using emerging materials. *Nat. Electron.* 7, 269-270 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-024-01155-7>.*

* DISCLAIMER: see disclaimer at the end of the report.

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1. Miscalculated mobility and reliability factor.

In their *Reply* to our *Matters Arising* (Podzorov, V., Bruevich, V. Safe practices for mobility evaluation in field-effect transistors and Hall effect measurements using emerging materials. *Nat. Electron.* 7, 266-268 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-024-01154-8>), A. Liu, H. Zhu, and YY. Noh (the authors) have included a plot of a linear-regime transfer characteristic of a CsSnI₃ thin-film transistor (TFT) and stated that these data suggest a mobility of 42 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ of this device (Fig. 1 below reproduces Fig. 1a of their Reply):

Figure 1. Digitizing Fig. 1a of the Reply. The digitized data points (red dots) of the linear-regime transfer curve (black open circles) are used below to correctly extract the linear-regime mobility, μ_{lin} .

Our analysis of this curve does not confirm the mobility of $42 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The linear-regime TFT mobility calculated from the above data using the Shockley model turns out to be much smaller. **Figure 2** below shows the digitized data of Fig. 1a of the Reply (black open circles are the same as the red dots in **Fig. 1** above) and our analysis. The linear mobility was calculated using the Shockley model for the linear regime (Eq. 1):

$$\mu_{lin} = \frac{L}{WC_iV_{DS}} \left(\frac{\partial I_{DS}}{\partial V_{GS}} \right). \quad (1)$$

We used two closely related methods to extract the mobility from these data: (1) fitting the transfer curve with a linear dependence (solid red line), and (2) differentiating the curve (solid blue squares) with the subsequent averaging of the derivative over the range $-40 \text{ V} < V_{GS} < 20 \text{ V}$. Both gave a very similar mobility $\mu_{lin} \approx 19.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (horizontal dashed lines), which is more than twice smaller than $42 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ listed by the authors in the Reply. The reliability factors added by the authors on their Fig. 1a of the Reply are irrelevant as well; the actual reliability of the stated mobility is $< 50\%$.

Figure 2. Plotting and analyzing digitized Fig. 1a of the Reply. The linear mobility of this device is $\mu_{lin} \approx 19.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is more than twice smaller than $42 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ listed by the authors in their Reply.

2. False statement regarding the TFT's independence of the gate voltage scan rate.

In their Reply, the authors attempted to discount the concern we raised in our Matters Arising regarding the very high Joule power densities (up to $\sim 200 \text{ W/cm}^2$) applied in their original work, which could have led to a degradation and/or non-room-temperature operation of their devices. They now argue in their Reply that "...the device character is independent of the V_{GS} sweep rate (Fig. 1b)". **Figure 3** below reproduces Fig. 1b of the Reply, and a closer look at it reveals two problems:

2.1. First, this Figure/data do not actually provide any information regarding the V_{GS} sweep rates used in these measurements. One cannot possibly figure out what sweep rates (in V/s) were used, as the magnitude of the "step" is not listed anywhere by the authors, and it is unclear whether the steps were the same or varied in this series of measurements. Nevertheless, we can think of these scan rates in relative sense.

2.2. As we have mentioned in our Matters Arising, the data appearance on log-scale plots can be deceiving, especially to a non-specialist or an inexperienced researcher. As shown in **Fig. 3** below, the difference between individual curves is actually very significant: both the absolute value of the maximum I_{DS} and the slope of the curves vary with the V_{GS} scanning speed by almost a factor of ~ 2 . Thus, the explicit statement of the authors in their Reply that "... the device character is independent of the V_{GS} sweep rate (Fig. 1b)" appears to be false. The data clearly show that there is a significant gate-voltage sweep rate dependence of the characteristics of CsSnI₃ perovskite TFTs.

Figure 3. The transfer characteristics of CsSnI₃ TFTs clearly depend on the V_{GS} sweep rate. A closer look at Fig. 1b of the Reply shows that the TFT's behavior does significantly depend on the gate voltage scan rate, which contradicts to the authors' explicit statement in the Reply. Plotting data on a log scale can mislead inexperienced readers.

3. Huge inconsistencies in the saturation regime mobilities.

Figure 4 below shows the digitized data of Fig. 1b of the Reply and the correct extraction of the mobilities from these curves. As we have pointed in our Matters Arising, the onset voltage, V_{onset} , of p -type transistors based on hole-doped semiconducting films can be shifted to positive voltages, which needs to be taken into account when determining where the saturation regime in such devices is occurring. In the transistor in **Fig. 4** (left panel), the onset voltage is very significant, $V_{\text{onset}} \approx 25$ V, indicating that the saturation regime (with a pinch-off of the channel) occurs in the range -15 V $< V_{\text{GS}} < 25$ V, while the operation at $V_{\text{GS}} < -15$ V should be more reminiscent of the linear regime of transistor operation (no pinch-off). Calculating the linear and saturation regime mobilities in these regions gives values much smaller than the mobilities listed by the authors in their Reply or their original 2022 *Nat. Electron.* paper. Namely, by using the Shockley model for the linear regime (Eq. 1 above) and saturation regime (Eq. 2 below):

$$\mu_{\text{sat}} = \frac{2L}{WC_i} \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{-I_{\text{DS}}}}{\partial V_{\text{GS}}} \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

we have obtained $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 11.7$ cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (middle panel) and $\mu_{\text{lin}} = 8.5$ cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (right panel). Note: for any of the curves included in Fig. 1b of the Reply, the correctly calculated μ is significantly smaller than 42 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹.

Figure 4. A mixed (saturation and linear) operation regime of the transistor shown in Fig. 1b of the Reply and digitizing these data to correctly extract the linear and saturation mobilities. The device exhibits a high $V_{\text{onset}} = 25$ V apparently due to a hole doping of the film, thus operating in the saturation regime to the right of the vertical dashed line (placed at $V_{\text{GS}} = -15$ V) and in the linear regime to the left of it (left panel). The mobilities extracted from the digitized data of Fig. 1b of the Reply using the Shockley model in these corresponding regimes are: $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 11.7$ cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (middle panel) and $\mu_{\text{lin}} = 8.5$ cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ (right panel), both of which contradict to the much higher values listed by the authors in their Reply and in the original 2022 *Nat. Electron.*

Why does this device have a much smaller mobility than those stated in the authors' original publication (2022 *Nat. Electron.*)? This device should belong to the same study and the same dataset as their original

study, because this Reply is supposed to be addressing our Matters Arising criticizing *that* specific paper with *that* specific dataset. However, in the original paper, the authors have stated that: “... *perovskite channels processed from the optimized precursor ensured high device reproducibility, showing average μ_{FE} of $51.4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and I_{on}/I_{off} exceeding 10^8 calculated from 100 devices in ten different batches*” and showed the following histogram (Fig. 5 below):

Figure 5. The statistics of measured devices shown in Fig. 1f of the authors’ original publication (2022 *Nat. Electron.*). The histogram shows that there were NO devices with a mobility smaller than $47 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

We would like to invite the authors to explain why they have not included in their histogram this particular device with $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 11.7 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1b of their Reply), which they have apparently had in their dataset since they are using it here.

4. Several misleading or wrong statements by the authors in their Reply.

Besides the huge inconsistencies with the reported μ and a misleading statement regarding the device stability against variations of the gate-voltage sweep rate, the authors have also included several statements in their Reply that appear to contradict the basic physics of charge transport in field-effect transistors (FETs).

4.1. For example, they stated:

Bruevich and Podzorov² recalculate the mobility based on raw data from our original Article (Fig. 1d in ref. 1). They use the reliability factor based on the nonlinearity in the $|I_{\text{DSI}}|^{1/2} - (V_{\text{GS}})$ curve to extract the mobility, which is often described for organic thin-film transistors (OTFTs)³. However, the adopted mode is typically suited to a highly ordered semiconductor, where linear transfer curves are expected, with constant carrier mobility. The applicability of linear evaluation for the extraction of mobility in polycrystalline disordered semiconductor systems has been discussed previously⁴. The non-

The model we use is the Shockley FET model, which is the *same* model used by the authors in their original paper (though, used incorrectly, as shown in our Matters Arising). This model works well and is commonly used for both ordered and disordered semiconductor FETs. It is also applicable to cases when the charge carrier mobility is not a constant and varies with the carrier density (or V_{GS}), as long as μ is the same everywhere along the channel. The problem here is not the model, but the fact that the authors misused it by incorrectly applying to their data (namely, by taking a derivative of a highly nonlinear, hysteretic and very noisy transfer curve and then picking up the value at a single high-spike point to calculate the mobility).

4.2. The authors also stated:

Based on the hole concentration values, the Hall mobility of $0.5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ calculated by Bruevich and Podzorov appears to be too low. Such a low film mobility would make it impossible to achieve high-mobility transistors, even with the TFT mobility of $13 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ recalculated by Bruevich and Podzorov. Various characterization meth-

This statement is wrong, indicating a lack of understanding of the Hall effect in thin films. It has been shown that the Hall voltage, and thus the Hall mobility, can be more significantly affected by the grain boundaries and/or other morphological inhomogeneities of thin films (such as oriented cracks, strain patterns, etc.) than the longitudinal FET mobility, leading to situations with $\mu_{FET} \gg \mu_{Hall}$ (see Refs. [14, 15] in our Matters Arising).

4.3. Another statement:

recalculated by Bruevich and Podzorov. Various characterization methods have demonstrated that 3D Sn^{2+} -based polycrystalline perovskite films possess high mobilities because of the intrinsically small hole effective masses and low Fröhlich interactions¹³⁻¹⁵. With Hall measure-

In our Matters Arising, we did not say that the mobility of Sn^{2+} -based perovskites cannot be high. We said that the mobility was incorrectly extracted (namely, significantly exaggerated) in the authors' 2022 *Nat. Electron.* paper.

4.4. Another statement:

effective masses and low Fröhlich interactions¹³⁻¹⁵. With Hall measurements, μ_{Hall} is mainly determined from fundamental film scattering, such as grain-boundary and impurity scattering (bulk transport). For the TFT μ_{FE} , charge-carrier transport under a gate bias is mainly confined near the semiconductor/dielectric interface. Such transport is much more sensitive to the hole traps existing in the bandgap near the valence and maximum, as well as to the interface roughness/defects of the gate dielectric and semiconductor layers. Generally, the TFT μ_{FE} is reported to be lower than μ_{Hall} , and this difference has been widely discussed for different semiconductors¹⁶⁻²¹. The degree

This statement refers to the fact that the Hall mobility we have roughly estimated from their data, $\mu_{\text{Hall}} \sim 0.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, is much smaller than the FET mobility of $\mu_{\text{FE}} \sim 13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ correctly re-calculated from their data. Here, again, this argument shows a lack of understanding of the physics of Hall effect and FET operation, or unwillingness to heed what we wrote in our Matters Arising. What we have shown is that estimating the *bulk* mobile carrier concentration, $n_{3\text{D}}$, by the two independent methods (1st - depleting the doped semiconducting film with a large positive gate voltage (V_{onset}), and 2nd - measuring the bulk (ungated) Hall effect) leads to drastically different values of $n_{3\text{D}}$, different by ~ 3 orders of magnitude. The primary parameter directly extracted from the Hall-effect measurements is the mobile carrier concentration $n_{3\text{D}}$, not the mobility μ_{Hall} . Both of these techniques probe the mobile carriers flowing in the bulk of the film, and therefore they address the same carriers and the same type of transport. Thus, the discussion of bulk vs. interfacial transport in Hall and FET measurements, respectively, is irrelevant here. In the Hall measurements, μ_{Hall} is a secondary parameter, because it is calculated (not directly measured) from the measured Hall carrier density and the film's conductivity. The fact that μ_{Hall} comes out so off ($\sim 0.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) in this case is simply an indication that something is awfully wrong with the Hall-effect measurements in the original paper.

4.5. We would also like to emphasize that most of our other technical concerns and questions about the original study (2022 *Nat. Electron.*) expressed in our Matters Arising, including, e.g., a complete lack of technical details on the Hall-effect measurements, have not been addressed by the authors in their Reply.

In Conclusion, here we reveal that, once again, the mobility of perovskite TFTs has been grossly miscalculated by A. Liu, H. Zhu, and YY. Noh, this time in their Reply to our Matters Arising. The actual mobilities correctly calculated from the data presented in the Reply are in the range $\mu \approx 8.5 - 19.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is much smaller than $42 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ listed by the authors. In addition, the statement by the

authors regarding the stability of the devices against variations of the gate-voltage sweep rate is clearly false.

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